

Motivated Reasoning and Disconfirmation in the Wason Selection Task

Shruti Shashidharan ■ Aankeet Gokkalgandhi

Abstract

Motivated reasoning is generally used when people are faced by some threat to their self or beliefs. If this trigger is not present, then people will reason in a way that will help them reach accurate conclusions rather than preferred conclusions. The aim of this study was to understand motivated reasoning through performance on the Wason Selection task. The proposed hypothesis was that people will perform better in the Wason selection task when they are presented with threatening content about their early death, than when they are presented with non-threatening content about early death of an outgroup. The methodology included using a between subjects experimental design with two levels to which the participants were assigned based on their availability. The first level consisted of presenting the participants with a hypothesis that was threatening to them, and the second level consisted of presenting a hypothesis that was non-threatening to them. The convenience sample of 176 participants (M=88, F=88), were in the age group of 18-25 years. The study was conducted online using the zoom app. The data was analyzed ($z=3.157$ at $\alpha=0.05$, $p=0.00079$, one tailed) and the results indicated that the performance on the Wason selection task was significantly better in the threatening condition as opposed to the non-threatening condition.

Keywords: Motivated reasoning. Wason selection task. Confirmation bias. Disconfirmation.

Shruti Shashidharan*

Master's Student of Applied Psychology, Department of Psychology,
Vivekanand Education Society's College of Arts, Science and Commerce,
Chembur, Mumbai, India
shruti.shashidharan.17323@ves.ac.in

Aankeet Gokkalgandhi

Assistant Professor of Psychology,
Vivekanand Education Society's College of Arts, Science and Commerce,
Chembur, Mumbai, India
aankeet.gandhi@ves.ac.in

*Corresponding author

Introduction

People believe what they want to believe and this is affected by their preferences. When people reason about conclusions they favor, their preferences influence the way evidence is gathered, arguments are processed, and memories of past experience are recalled. These processes are affected by people's motivations, which lead to biased conclusions. People who want to arrive at a particular conclusion will construct justifications accordingly to persuade a person who doesn't agree with them. Our motivated beliefs are therefore guided by motivated reasoning.

Motivated reasoning is a type of reasoning in which people analyze information in a biased fashion to reach preferred conclusions that have favorable implications for the self. The "Can I/ Must I" model was proposed by Gilovich (1991), which describes the evidential standards that people employ when reasoning about different propositions. According to this model, people use the "can I" questioning when dealing with agreeable propositions as it provides a more permissive standard of evidence. Therefore, a person will engage in partial, biased and superficial reasoning and is more likely to fall prey to confirmation bias. Confirmation bias is a tendency to look for information or evidence that will confirm a preferred hypothesis, that is, people have a bias towards verification. This is especially pronounced for people who want to accept a proposition as valid. On the other hand, people use the "must I" questioning when dealing with disagreeable propositions as it is a more stringent evidential standard. This leads to a more thorough evaluation of the information. Thus, people who have a skeptical mindset are less likely to fall prey to errors in reasoning as they are more likely to identify any limitations and flaws, thereby, increasing the chances of rejecting the information.

Individuals more readily tend to accept information that is consistent with their preferences as compared to information that is inconsistent with their preferences. Information that one wants to believe is seen as more valid or accurate as they approach such information with a particular set of cognitive biases. Therefore, a person will search for evidences and instances from past behavior that is likely to support their desired goals. A study by Ditto et al. (1998) showed that preference inconsistent information elicits more sensitive information processing in people, because they do not want to believe that information, as compared to information processing in people viewing preference consistent information. People engage in more effortful cognitive processing when faced with preference inconsistent information, to search for alternative explanations that produce uncertainty with respect to the validity of that information. In case of preference consistent information, people unthinkingly accept the validity of the information at face value and do not try to construct judgments for the same quantity of processing view (Ditto & Lopez, 1992).

Another study was conducted by Munro et al. (2009), to see the effect of self-affirmation on confirmation bias and motivated reasoning. Self-affirmation was done by letting the participants write about a value that is important to them. Threatening information elicits a skeptical mindset, however, people who have been self-affirmed are more likely to show less effective reasoning strategies, such as confirmation bias, when faced with threatening information. This is because the sting from the threatening information is reduced by the opportunity for self-affirmation prior to the presentation of the threat. Thus, their self-concept is not threatened enough to motivate them to try and disprove the threatening information. Therefore, people who have been self-affirmed and receive threatening information show reasoning that is similar to people who receive non-threatening information. On the other hand, people exposed to threatening information who do not get an opportunity for self-affirmation tend to adopt a more skeptical mindset and are less likely to show confirmation bias.

An experimental study was conducted by Dawson et al. (2002). The logic behind the experiment is that people prefer to approach agreeable propositions with a confirmation bias and disagreeable propositions with a disconfirmation bias. The Wason selection task was used here. It is a logic puzzle and is one of the most famous tasks to assess deductive reasoning. In this task, four cards and a rule is presented. The problem solver has to test the rule by flipping over the relevant cards. In a modification of this task, the problem solver is told specifically to choose any 2 cards only. For example, if the rule is, “*If there is a vowel on one side, then there is an even number on the other side*”, and the four cards are A, D, 4, and 7, then the correct cards to be selected are card A and card 7. This is because the appropriate strategy for solving the Wason selection task is to look for disconfirmation, that is, card p and not q. People generally tend to look for confirming evidence (confirmation bias) and therefore, solve the task incorrectly. However, if presented with a rule that if correct, will be threatening to the person, they will be more motivated to seek disconfirmation and thereby, solve the task correctly. In the first experiment, the aim was to study motivated reasoning and performance on the Wason selection task. Participants who were presented with threatening information (early death of self) would be more likely to perform better as compared to participants who were presented with non-threatening information (early death of outgroup), in the Wason selection task.

This effect was also seen in the case of gender stereotypes and ethnicity. Dawson et al. (2002) said that people who receive information that is threatening to their gender or ethnic identity are more likely to solve the Wason selection task correctly as compared to people who receive favorable information about their gender or ethnicity, or negative information about the opposite gender or some other ethnic group. The concept is that people will be more motivated to disprove something that is threatening to their self-concept and is against their beliefs as opposed to something that is not threatening and is consistent with their beliefs.

Overall, several research studies support the idea that motivated reasoning leads people to adopt a skeptical mindset when presented with information that is threatening to their beliefs, values and self-concept. Therefore, they are more likely to be engaged in disconfirmation.

This study is based on Dawson et al. (2002), which it was hypothesized that participants in the threatening condition will perform better in the Wason selection task when presented with information that is threatening to them than when presented with information that is non-threatening.

Methodology

The sample selected for this study consisted of undergraduate and post graduate college students from the age of 18-25 years. The sample size was 176, with 88 participants in the threatening condition and 88 participants in the non-threatening condition. There were equal number of male and female participants in both the conditions of the independent variable (IV), that is, 44 males and 44 females in each condition. The sample was a convenience sample and no random assignment was done. They were selected and assigned to the conditions based on availability.

The design used was independent sample design or between subjects experimental design, with one independent variable having two levels - threatening condition (in which participants were to test a hypothesis that indicated the early death of their own emotional instability, that is, high/low), and non-threatening condition (in which the participants had to test a hypothesis that indicated early death of the emotional instability level opposite of their own, that is, if the participant scored high on the emotional lability scale, they were presented with the hypothesis that low emotional instability will lead to early death). The dependent variable (DV) was dichotomous (performance on the Wason selection task). Participants who solved the task correctly (picked card p and not q) got a score of 1, and participants who solved the task incorrectly (picked any other combination of cards) got a score of 0.

The study was conducted online through zoom platform. The participants' demographic details, such as name, age, gender, and emotional state, were collected and rapport was established. Once they were comfortable and ready to begin, the instructions were delivered both verbally and visually (screen sharing the slide) to ensure better understanding of the task. The first phase of the instructions directed them to answer a questionnaire measuring emotional regulation [7-item affective lability scale, Moore et al. (1997)]. Then they were presented the questionnaire on the screen and were instructed to give their answers aloud.

The scale was a 5-point Likert rating scale. The responses were carefully noted by the experimenter. After the participant finished answering all the questions, their responses were scored. They were then shown their results, that is whether they are high in emotional instability (average score 3 or above 3) or low in emotional instability (average score below 3). Then they were given the second phase of the instructions in which they were presented with a research hypothesis about emotional instability and early death and were asked to test it. In one condition, the participants having high/low emotional instability were told a threatening hypothesis that “high/low instability leads to early death” (threatening condition), whereas in the other condition, the Ps having high/ low instability were told a non-threatening hypothesis about early death of an out-group, that is, “low/high instability leads to early death” (non-threatening condition). The slide was changed to display the four cards and the hypothesis. The participants were given as much time as they needed to make their selection of the cards (any two cards had to be selected to test the hypothesis).

Their response was noted by the experimenter and the relevant PTQs were asked. Then they were thoroughly debriefed about the purpose of the experiment. Explanations for the two conditions of the IV, the expected response for either condition, as well as the correct solution to the card selection task was given. The experimenter specifically emphasized that there was no such existing research about a person's emotional instability and early death, and therefore, the participant had nothing to worry about. Any queries or questions they had regarding the experiment was answered, and they were thanked for participating.

Results

The data for 176 participants was collected and compiled to find the proportion of correct responses in each condition. It is calculated by dividing the total number of correct responses in each condition by the total number of responses in each condition. The total number of correct responses in the threatening condition is 35 out of a total of 88 scores. The total number of correct responses in the non-threatening condition is 16 out of a total of 88 scores.

Table 1 Proportion of correct responses

Condition	Proportion of correct responses
Threatening	0.3977
Non-threatening	0.1818

Analysis

The z score calculator for two population proportions was used (www.socscistatistics.com), because the DV is in nominal scale and the responses are dichotomous. The obtained z score is 3.157, at $\alpha=0.05$, $p=0.00079$, one tailed. The obtained results of the two sample test of proportions indicate that the z statistic ($z=3.157$) was beyond the critical z with p value being less than .05 ($p=0.00079$). Therefore, the result is significant. So we can say that there is evidence to support the hypothesis (alternate hypothesis) that the proportion of people solving the WST task will be higher in the threatening condition as compared to the non-threatening condition. That is people are more likely to seek out disconfirming evidence when presented with a threatening rule.

Discussion and Conclusion

The Wason selection task is a logic puzzle that is used to assess deductive reasoning. Most people find it difficult to solve this task correctly as looking for disconfirming information is necessary to reach the correct solution. Generally, people have the tendency towards confirmation bias that is, looking for evidence that will confirm their beliefs. In the case of motivated reasoning, an important trigger is some threat to one's self-concept or beliefs. Therefore, when a person is faced with such a threat, they are more likely to process the information more deeply, so as to evaluate all possible conclusions, and find evidence that can disconfirm the information. This in turn reduces the likelihood of falling prey to the confirmation bias. A tendency towards disconfirmation is necessary to solve the Wason selection task correctly and therefore, it was expected that participants in the threatening condition would be more likely to perform better in the task than those in the non-threatening condition.

In this study, the participants either received a threatening hypothesis (early death of self) or a non-threatening hypothesis to test (early death of out-group member). The participants who received a hypothesis indicating early death of an out-group (opposite of their emotional instability) were not threatened by it, and therefore were less motivated to disprove it. They were more likely to use confirmation bias and therefore, performed poorly in the Wason selection task. On the other hand, participants who tested a hypothesis that was threatening to them, that is, it indicated early death of their own emotional instability, were more likely to look for contrary evidence to disprove the statement. They did not engage in confirmation bias and hence, performed better in the Wason selection task. The results obtained for this sample is in line with past research, and provided support for the hypothesis of the experiment.

The reasoning strategies of the participants can be attributed to the subjective interpretation of the statements they were shown. There was negative information of two types - one indicated a direct threat to the person, whereas the other did not. People who were presented with a negative statement that indicated the early death of an out-group did not perform better at the Wason selection task therefore, we can rule out the possibility that negative information in general elicited a disconfirmatory strategy. There is clear evidence that the specific threat induced by the negative statement indicating the early death of oneself led to improved performance in the Wason selection task. However, the strategies used by the participants in this study might not necessarily transfer to other situations or on more abstract versions of the Wason selection task. The approach used to solve the task was more about concluding whether the proposition represented correct information, rather than focusing on whether one was using the appropriate strategies to form conclusions.

Typically, motivated reasoning leads to improved reasoning, with people forming judgments of higher quality when faced with threatening information. However, in the case of health threats, such as "smoking leads to cancer", people use this same mechanism of motivated reasoning to endorse preferred conclusions like, "people who don't smoke also suffer from cancer", "there are smokers who do not die of cancer", and "I exercise and eat healthy, so it counteracts the effects of smoking," among others. which is counter-productive to developing positive health behaviors. People who do not have faith in a particular treatment will more likely disregard the reports if they have minor spelling errors. For example, even in the face of contrary evidence that provides large support to the effectiveness of vaccines and dire consequences of not getting vaccinated, anti-vaxxers will bring up rare instances of vaccine failure, where it caused negative effects to health or in extreme cases, led to death. In the political context, poor judgments are made when a person discredits everything a disliked politician says, and endlessly supports a liked politician no matter what they say or do. Therefore, it is important to understand motivated reasoning and how people approach several propositions to reach conclusions as disconfirmation does not always have a positive effect or lead to better reasoning.

A possible modification to this study is to use gender stereotypes to induce threat to one's identity and self-concept. Instead of presenting them with hypothesis indicating their own early death or early death of an out-group, they can be presented with common gender stereotypes that is either negative or positive. It can be hypothesized that the participants who receive a negative stereotype of their own gender will be more likely to perform better in the Wason selection task, as compared to the participants who receive a negative stereotype of the opposite gender, or receive a positive stereotype of their own gender. A possible suggestion for future study would be to see if people with a negativistic bias towards life (such as people with depression) would perform correctly or incorrectly in a similar Wason selection task. This would help to understand if conditional reasoning deteriorates in people with mental illness.

Data Availability

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the authors, upon reasonable request.

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